

Knowledge and Perception regarding Harm Reduction Strategies for Substance Abuse among Nurses in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Substance abuse has escalated globally, contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality, and prompting increased attention to harm reduction strategies aimed at minimizing risks associated with substance use without requiring complete abstinence. This study investigated the knowledge and perception of nurses in Southwest Nigeria regarding harm reduction strategies for substance abuse management. Using a descriptive cross-sectional design, data were collected from 202 nurses across four hospitals through a standardized questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and Fisher's exact test. Although most respondents (79.2%) had previously heard of harm reduction, the findings revealed that a large proportion demonstrated poor knowledge (90.1%) and more than half exhibited poor perception (54.5%) of harm reduction approaches. These results indicate a substantial gap between awareness and actual understanding of harm reduction principles among nurses, underscoring the need for targeted educational interventions and capacity-building efforts to strengthen their competence in implementing harm reduction practices effectively within clinical settings.

Keywords: Harm reduction strategies, Knowledge, Nurses, Perception, Substance abuse,

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Introduction

Substance abuse, which includes both alcohol and other drugs of abuse, has been identified as a serious issue affecting people global (Shmulewitz et al., 2023). Substance abuse causes 11.8 million global deaths annually, primarily due to overdoses of substances or the chance of dying young from prolonged drug usage. This can lead to medical conditions like HIV, hepatitis, and liver disease, as well as smoking, diabetes, heart disease, stroke, lung and other malignancies (Ritchie et al. 2019). Social consequences include homelessness, financial difficulties, interpersonal relationships, legal issues, and work-related issues (Pauly et al., 2021; Ogunjobi et al., 2023). However, successful quitting cases are very low, incidence of relapse are higher, and many people want to get involved, attaining substantial rates of quitting in the drug abuse community seems to be an unachievable goal (O'Leary & Polosa 2020).

Drug abuse has grown to be an important problem for public health, necessitating the evolution of policies and specialized services to address the issue (Soares et al., 2020). There are two primary approaches to treating substance use disorders: abstinence and harm reduction (Lopez et al., 2021). Abstinence measures involve pharmacotherapy and behavioral therapy, such as cognitive behavioral therapy, to help users quit and alter their perspectives and actions toward illicit drug use. Harm reduction is a social movement designed to lessen negative impacts of drug use on health, social relationships, and the economy. It acknowledges the freedom of drug users to consume drugs safely and upholds their rights and dignity, serving as a substitute for abstinence-focused programs and policies (Khan et al., 2022). The National Harm Reduction Coalition describes harm reduction as a strategy for public health that attempt to lessen the harmful effects of drug abuse, including physical, social, and economic, without focusing on abstinence (National Harm Reduction Coalition). It involves policies, initiatives, and methods that seek to lessen drug use's harmful consequences without emphasizing abstinence.

Nurses are crucial in identifying and addressing substance abuse issues, often being the first to notice and often the only point of contact for drug users. They can help patients to think about methods to cut back on their drug usage by using strategies like motivational interviews and short interventions (Hamilton et al., 2021) and in order to increase trust and make health care more accessible, harm reduction in nursing practice needs to be expanded (Onu et al., 2020; Adekola et al., 2022). Therefore, this study sought to investigate the knowledge and perception of nurses on harm reduction strategies for substance abuse in Southwest, Nigeria. The findings could be used to orientate nurses, especially mental health/psychiatric nurses on the need to learn and advocate for the utilization of harm reduction strategies for substance abuse management.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was employed for this study, which was conducted in four major hospitals across Southwest Nigeria: Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti (FETHI), Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital (EKSUTH), Ado-Ekiti, Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Owo, and the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Yaba (FNPHY), Lagos State. These institutions provide both in-patient and out-patient services for individuals with psychiatric disorders and those managing substance abuse. The study setting was selected to ensure representation of facilities that routinely provide comprehensive mental health and substance abuse care within the region.

A multistage sampling technique was adopted. At Stage 1, three states were Ekiti, Ondo, and Lagos were randomly selected from the six states in Southwest Nigeria. Stage 2 involved purposive selection of major hospitals within these states that manage psychiatric and substance abuse cases. Stage 3 applied proportionate stratification to determine the appropriate sample size from each hospital. At Stage 4, convenience sampling was used to recruit participants for the quantitative component of the study. The study population comprised mental health and psychiatric nurses working in the selected hospitals across the three states.

Sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane's formula $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ where,

n signifies sample size

N signifies the population under study

e signifies sample error (0.05)

Therefore

Number of mental health/psychiatric nurses in Federal Teaching Hospital (FETHI), Ido Ekiti = 16

Number of mental health/psychiatric nurses in Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital (EKSUTH), Ado Ekiti = 8

Number of mental health/psychiatric nurses in Federal Medical Center (FMC), Owo = 10

Number of mental health/psychiatric nurses in Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Yaba (FNPHY), Lagos = 300

$N = N(\text{FETHI}) + N(\text{EKSUTH}) + N(\text{FMC}) + N(\text{FNPHY})$

$N = 16 + 8 + 10 + 300 = 334$

$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

$334 / 1 + 334(0.05)^2$

$= 334 / 1.84$

182

An attrition rate of 10% was given for poorly completed questionnaire or non-response.

Attrition Rate = Previous sample size \times standard attrition rate

Standard Attrition Rate = 1

$= \frac{182 \times 10}{10 - 1}$

10-1

$= 1820 / 9$

$= 202$

Therefore, 202 mental health/psychiatric nurses were selected proportionately to participate in the study

Table 1: Proportionate stratified sampling

S/N	Name	Calculations	Total
1	FETHI	$(16/334) \times 202$	10
2	EKSUTH	$(8/334) \times 202$	5
3	FMC, Owo	$(10/334) \times 202$	6
4	FNPHY	$(300/334) \times 202$	181
TOTAL			202

Therefore, 10 respondents were selected in FETHI, 5 respondents were selected in EKSUTH, 6 respondents were selected in FMC, Owo, and 181 respondents were selected in FNPHY to participate in the study. The inclusion criteria for this study include all nurses who willingly participated and were present during the time of data collection. Non-mental health/psychiatric nurses were excluded from the study. Mental health/psychiatric nurses who were on leave and were not available at the time of data collection were excluded.

The harm reduction questionnaire devised by Hobden and Cunningham (2006) and and Goddard's Harm Reduction Acceptability Scale (HRAS) designed by Goddard (2003) were adapted. The instrument is made up of three (3) sections, the first part contained (7) items on the sociodemographic characteristics of the nurses, the section B contained eight (8) items on the knowledge level of nurses on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse and the last section C contained seventeen (17) items on the perception to harm reduction strategies against substance abuse. Quantitative data were cleaned, coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 for analysis. Descriptive analysis was done using frequency counts, pie chart, bar chart, standard deviation, to describe study population as related to dependent and independent variables. The probability p-value < 0.05 was taken as the minimum level of significance and the result were presented in tables and chart.

Approval to conduct the study was obtained from Research and Ethics committee of Afe Babalola University Ado-Ekiti with the protocol number ABUADHREC/12/02/2024/336. Approval was obtained from Research and Ethical Committee of Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti with the protocol number ERC/2023/12/14/1056B, Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital with the protocol number EKSUTH/A67/2023/12/014, Federal Medical Center, Owo with the protocol number NHREC/FMC/OWO-HREC/002, and Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Yaba, Lagos state with the protocol number FNPHY/HREC/2023/001/12/226 before conducting the research. In addition, consent form was filled out and duly signed by all the respondents following a proper and thorough explanation of the significance and objectives of the study.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses are presented in Table 2. The table reveals that most (69.8%) of them were females, predominantly within the age range 41-60years (48.0%), Christians (77.7%), and Yoruba ethnic affiliation (65.3%).

Table: 2 Socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses (N=202)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	61	30.2
	Female	141	69.8
Age (years)	20 and below	16	7.9
	21-40	86	42.6
	41-60	97	48.0
	61 and above	3	1.5
Religion	Christianity	157	77.7
	Islam	45	22.3
Ethnicity	Hausa	6	3.0
	Igbo	60	29.7

	Yoruba	132	65.3
	Others	4	2.0
Highest level of education	Diploma	95	47.0
	Bachelor's degree	90	44.6
	Master's degree	17	8.4
	Total	202	100.0

Majority 160(79.2%) of the Nurses have heard about harm reduction

Figure 1: Piechart showing awareness of nurses of harm reduction strategies

Table 3 showed the level of knowledge of nurses on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse by hospitals. More than three-quarter (90.1%) of the nurses had poor knowledge on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse, with a mean score of 9.23 ± 7.2 and further analysis showed that knowledge varies across the selected hospitals.

Table 3: Knowledge of nurses on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse (N=202)

Variable	Category	FETHI IDO-EKITI	EKSUTH ADO-EKITI	FMC, OWO	FNPHY LAGOS	TOTAL
Which harm reduction strategy against substance	Needle and syringe programme	4(40.0)	2(40.0)	3(50.0)	63(34.8)	72(35.6)
	Prescribing naloxone and opioid	2(20.0)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	31(17.1)	37(18.3)
	Controlled drinking programme	0(0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	19(10.5)	22(10.9)

abuse do you know?	Giving free condoms to drug users	0(0)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	18(9.9)	22(10.9)
	Nicotine Replacement Therapy	2(20.0)	1(20.0)	3(50.0)	31(17.1)	37(18.3)
	Prescribing naltrexone and alcohol	1(10.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	12(6.6)	15(7.4)
	Community education on harm reduction	0(0)	2(40.0)	3(50.0)	83(45.9)	88(43.6)
Definition of harm reduction	Reducing harm from substance use incurred by the individual by reducing or eliminating the use of that substance	5(50.0)	3(60.0)	3(50.0)	75(41.4)	86(42.6)
	Reducing the harm from substance use incurred by the individual and reducing their use of that substance	3(30.0)	3(60.0)	2(33.3)	79(43.6)	87(43.1)
	Reducing the harm from substance use incurred by the individual without necessarily reducing their use of that substance	5(50.0)	3(60.0)	1(16.7)	29(16.0)	38(18.8)
	Reducing the harm associated with substance use to the community or society as a whole	0(0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	31(17.1)	34(16.8)
	Reducing the harm associated with substance use	2(20.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	27(14.9)	31(15.3)
	Most important elements of harm reduction	Disease reduction	2(20.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	37(20.4)
Empowering clients	2(20.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	41(23.8)	45(22.3)	
Improving the quality of life of clients	1(10.0)	0(0)	2(33.3)	65(35.9)	68(33.7)	
Reducing negative consequences associated with	4(40.0)	3(60.0)	4(66.7)	48(26.5)	59(29.2)	

	drug/alcohol use					
	Education/awareness on the part of the client	3(30.0)	1(20.0)	3(50.0)	39(21.5)	46(22.8)
	Education/awareness on the part of the community	1(10.0)	0(0)	2(33.3)	27(14.9)	30(14.9)
	Client's choice	1(10.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	14(7.7)	17(8.4)
	Flexibility/options	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	20(11.0)	21(10.4)
	Empathy	3(30.0)	2(40.0)	0(0)	26(14.4)	31(15.3)
	Accurate assessment	0(0)	0(0)	2(33.3)	18(9.9)	20(9.9)
Most appealing aspects of harm reduction	Disease reduction	2(20.0)	2(40.0)	3(50.0)	46(25.4)	53(26.2)
	Reduced health costs	4(40.0)	2(40.0)	3(50.0)	47(26.0)	56(27.7)
	May provide a gateway/bridge into treatment	3(30.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	35(19.3)	40(19.8)
	It is more palatable to clients than abstinence	0(0)	1(20.0)	4(66.7)	40(22.1)	45(22.3)
	Client's choice	2(20.0)	0(0)	0(0)	19(10.5)	21(10.4)
	It is non-judgmental	6(60.0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	29(16.0)	38(18.8)
	It is pragmatic/practical	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	22(12.2)	23(11.4)
	It provides flexibility and options	2(20.0)	2(40.0)	4(66.7)	17(9.4)	25(12.4)
	It empowers the client	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	32(17.7)	33(16.3)
	It is client-centered	0(0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	21(17.1)	24(11.9)
It is appropriate for some clients	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	12(6.6)	13(6.4)	
Most troubling aspects of harm reduction	It is not appropriate for or in the best interest of all clients	0(0)	1(20.0)	0(0)	46(25.4)	47(23.3)
	It is often misunderstood and misapplied	2(20.0)	2(40.0)	3(50.0)	71(39.2)	78(38.6)
	It creates moral and ethical dilemmas for the community	5(50.0)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	23(12.7)	32(15.8)
	It creates moral and ethical dilemmas for the community	1(10.0)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	10(5.5)	13(6.4)
	Negative public attitudes	2(20.0)	3(60.0)	2(33.3)	18(9.9)	25(12.4)

	It is difficult to use illicit drugs safely	1(10.0)	1((20.0)	2(33.3)	22(12.2)	26(12.9)
	Abstinence is better	4(40.0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	33(18.2)	40(19.8)
	Harm reduction should be accomplished by counselling	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	29(16.0)	30(14.9)
Harm reduction strategy is	An acceptable strategy regardless of the final goals for all clients (mild, moderate and severe substance use disorders)	10(100.0)	3(60.0)	4(66.7)	125(70.6)	142(70.3)
	An acceptable strategy for only clients with severe SUD	0(0)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	52(28.7)	56(27.7)
Knowledge score of nurses on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse						
		Frequency		Percent		
Knowledge score	GOOD (>50%)	20		9.9		
	POOR (<50%)	182		90.1		
Mean±SD		9.23±7.2				
	Total	202		100.0		

Table 4 and Table 5 revealed nurses' perception of harm reduction strategies against substance abuse. According to nurses' perception of harm reduction strategies against substance abuse, more than half (54.5%) of the nurses had poor perception on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse, with a mean score of 50.2±7.36.

Table 4: Perception of nurses regarding harm reduction strategies against substance abuse

Variable	Category	FETHI IDO- EKITI F(%)	EKSUT H ADO- EKITI F(%)	FMC, OWO F(%)	FNPHY LAGOS F(%)	TOTAL Mean±SD
I feel good about harm reduction as a treatment goal for drug users?	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	2(1.2)	3.37±0.70
	D	4(44.4)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	8(4.6)	
	A	3(33.3)	3(60.0)	3(50.0)	76(43.9)	
	S	2(22.2)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	87(50.3)	
The community will feel good about harm reduction for drug users	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	2(1.2)	3.28±0.71
	D	4(44.4)	2(40.0)	0(0)	14(8.1)	
	A	5(55.6)	2(40.0)	4(66.7)	78(45.1)	
	SA	0(0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	79(45.7)	
People with alcohol or substance	SD	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	5(2.9)	3.02±0.76

problems who want to reduce, but not eliminate their alcohol or drug use are in denial	D	3(33.3)	0(0)	0(0)	29(17.0)	
	A	6(66.7)	4(80.0)	3(50.0)	91(53.2)	
	SA	0(0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	46(26.9)	
Injecting drug users should be taught how to use bleach to sterilize their injecting equipment	SD	0(0)	0(0)	2(33.3)	34(19.7)	2.59±1.08
	D	1(11.1)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	43(24.9)	
	A	7(77.8)	3(60.0)	2(33.3)	50(28.9)	
	SA	1(11.1)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	46(26.6)	
The choice of treatment outcome goals (for example, abstinence, reduced use of drugs or alcohol) should be discussed with all people seeking help for drug or alcohol problems	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	12(6.9)	3.14±0.86
	D	2(22.2)	0(0)	0(0)	19(11.0)	
	A	6(66.7)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	73(42.2)	
	SA	1(11.1)	3(60.0)	4(66.7)	69(39.9)	
In order to reduce problems such as crime and health risks, doctors should be permitted to treat drug addiction by prescribing heroin and similar drugs	SD	0(0)	0(0)	2(33.3)	64(37.0)	2.17±1.04
	D	1(11.1)	3(60.0)	1(16.7)	46(26.6)	
	A	7(77.8)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	39(22.5)	
	SA	1(11.1)	0(0)	1(16.7)	24(13.9)	
Drug users should be given accurate information about how to use drugs more safely (for example, how to avoid overdose or related health hazards)	SD	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	23(13.3)	2.86±0.95
	D	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	24(13.9)	
	A	5(55.6)	5(100)	2(33.3)	82(47.4)	
	SA	4(44.4)	0(0)	3(50.0)	44(25.4)	
People with drug or alcohol problems who are not willing to accept abstinence as their treatment outcome goals should be offered treatment that aims to reduce the harm associated with their continued drugs or alcohol use	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	6(3.5)	3.03±0.80
	D	0(0)	1(20.0)	0(0)	39(22.5)	
	A	8(88.9)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	73(42.2)	
	SA	1(11.1)	2(40.0)	4(66.7)	55(31.8)	
Measures designed to reduce the harm associated with drug or alcohol use are acceptable only if they eventually lead clients to pursue abstinence	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	4(2.3)	3.05±0.75
	D	1(11.1)	0(0)	4(66.7)	30(17.3)	
	A	7(77.8)	2(40.0)	1(16.7)	89(51.4)	
	SA	1(11.1)	3(60.0)	1(16.7)	50(28.9)	
People with drug and alcohol problems may be more likely to seek professional help if they are offered at least some treatment options that do not focus on abstinence	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	10(5.8)	3.04±0.89
	D	3(33.3)	1(20.0)	0(0)	27(15.6)	
	A	4(44.4)	3(60.0)	3(50.0)	74(42.8)	
	SA	2(22.2)	1(20.0)	3(50.0)	62(35.8)	
People whose drug use is stable should be trained to teach other drug users how to use	SD	2(22.2)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	24(13.9)	2.72±1.03

drugs more safely (for example, how to inject more safely)	D	3(33.3)	0(0)	3(50.0)	33(19.1)	
	A	4(44.4)	3(60.0)	1(16.7)	64(37.0)	
	SA	0(0)	1(20.0)	0(0)	52(30.1)	
It is possible to use drugs without necessarily misusing or abusing drugs	SD	1(11.1)	3(60.0)	1(16.7)	20(11.6)	2.74±1.0 1
	D	3(33.3)	0(0)	2(33.3)	38(22.0)	
	A	5(55.6)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	63(36.4)	
	SA	0(0)	0(0)	1(16.7)	52(30.1)	
Pamphlets that educate drug users about safer drug use should be detailed and explicit, even if those pamphlets are offensive to some people	SD	0(0)	1(20.0)	0(0)	4(2.3)	3.09±0.7 1
	D	0(0)	2(40.0)	2(33.3)	22(12.7)	
	A	9(100)	2(40.0)	1(16.7)	94(54.3)	
	SA	0(0)	0(0)	3(50.0)	53(30.6)	
Substitute such as methadone should be prescribed for a limited period of time	SD	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	13(7.5)	2.80±0.8 6
	D	0(0)	1(20.0)	0(0)	51(29.5)	
	A	7(77.8)	4(80.0)	4(66.7)	74(42.8)	
	SA	2(22.2)	0(0)	2(33.3)	35(20.2)	
To reduce the spread of HIV and other blood-borne diseases, drug injectors should be given access to clean injecting equipment	SD	0(0)	0(0)	2(33.3)	10(5.8)	2.95±0.8 7
	D	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	38(22.0)	
	A	7(77.8)	5(100)	3(50.0)	73(42.2)	
	SA	2(22.2)	0(0)	1(16.7)	52(30.1)	
People with alcohol or drug problems should be praised for making changes such as cutting down on their alcohol/drug consumption or switching from injectable drugs to oral drugs	SD	1(11.1)	1(20.0)	1(16.7)	10(5.8)	2.82±0.8 4
	D	2(22.2)	0(0)	1(16.7)	35(20.2)	
	A	6(66.7)	4(80.0)	1(16.7)	92(53.2)	
	SA	0(0)	0(0)	3(50.0)	36(20.8)	
Abstinence should be the only acceptable treatment goal for people who use illegal	SD	1(11.1)	0(0)	2(33.3)	7(4.0)	3.11±0.8 7

drugs and alcohol	D	3(33.3)	0(0)	0(0)	26(15.0)
	A	5(55.6)	4(80.0)	2(33.3)	69(39.9)
	SA	0(0)	1(20.0)	2(33.3)	71(41.0)
Total		9(100)	5(100)	6(100)	173(100)

Table 5: Perception of nurses to harm reduction strategies against substance abuse

Perception score	Category	Frequency	Percent
	Good ($\geq 75\%$)	92	45.5
	Poor ($< 75\%$)	110	54.5
	Total	202	100.0
	Mean \pm SD	50.2 \pm 7.36	

F=Frequency, SD= Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, A= Agree, SA= Strongly Agree

Discussion of Findings

This study was carried out in a stand-alone psychiatric hospital, teaching hospital of tertiary institutions and a government owned hospital and this can be compared with a study carried out by Onu et al. (2020). In the study carried out by Onu et al. (2020), all the respondents (100%) had heard about harm reduction strategy, however, this is not in agreement with the quantitative aspect of this study as 79.2% of the Nurses have heard about harm reduction. Of the HRS programmes that the respondents are knowledgeable of in our study, community education on harm reduction, needle and syringe programme, nicotine replacement therapy, and naloxone and opioid are the ones the respondents have good knowledge of, the study of Onu et al. (2020) was not in agreement with this study on the level of knowledge of HRS among respondents, the four harm reduction strategies that their respondents are knowledgeable of are needle exchange, methadone replacement, controlled drinking, and free condom. Overall, most of their respondents have a good knowledge of harm reduction strategy whereas most of the respondents in our study have poor knowledge of HRS even though they are aware of its existence.

According to nurses' perception of harm reduction strategies against substance abuse, more than half of the nurses had poor perception on harm reduction strategies against substance abuse. Responses among participants pointed that abstinence is preferred over HRS for example, measures designed to reduce the harm associated with drug or alcohol use are acceptable only if they eventually lead clients to pursue abstinence. This result is in contrast with the results of Javadi et al. (2021) in their study to examine attitudes toward HRS among substance use treatment professionals, they found out that treatment professionals generally had a positive perception of HR interventions as more than 80% agreed that HRS should be discussed with clients. It is also in contrast with Ortega (2022) which focused on the examination of the attitudes towards substance use treatment approaches by substance use

professionals using Goddard's Harm Reduction Acceptability Scale. Our findings of general poor perception as reported by the respondents may be explained by the belief system of the people in Southwest, Nigeria on substance abuse as it is generally seen as a form of juvenile delinquency and harm reduction should only be carried out with the end goal of abstinence for individuals that are not willing to accept abstinence at the moment.

Conclusion

The findings demonstrate that although most nurses were aware of harm reduction strategies, their depth of knowledge and overall perception of these strategies remained limited. While nurses expressed varying viewpoints on the components, acceptability, and ethical considerations of harm reduction, the general trend reflected uncertainty and mixed attitudes toward its practical application in substance abuse management. These results highlight a clear gap between awareness and informed understanding, indicating the need for strengthened capacity-building initiatives.

Recommendations

1. Healthcare institutions should implement structured training programmes that provide nurses with comprehensive, evidence-based knowledge of harm reduction principles, techniques, and their applicability in substance abuse management.
2. Hospital management and policymakers should integrate harm reduction content into continuing professional development requirements to ensure consistent exposure, improved understanding, and sustained competence among nursing staff.
3. Clear institutional guidelines on harm reduction should be developed and disseminated to help nurses translate theoretical awareness into practical, ethical, and culturally aligned clinical interventions.
4. Collaboration between hospitals, public health agencies, and community-based organisations should be strengthened to create supportive environments where nurses can observe, practise, and refine harm reduction approaches as part of multidisciplinary care..

Authors' Contributions

OC designed this study, collected the data, analyzed it and wrote the manuscript. EE participated in the design of the study and supervised the work. JA supervised the manuscript and participated in the drafting of the manuscript. All authors approved the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in this work and the study was fully funded by the authors.

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